

Mucosal Vaccination in Animals

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Introduction

Generally infectious agents invade the body through mucosal surfaces, especially the respiratory and digestive tracts. It makes sense therefore for vaccine antigens to be administered by the same route. Apparently, by mimicking the natural route, vaccines will trigger immune responses on these surfaces and ideally, block pathogen invasion.

When a systemic immune response is triggered by injected antigen, effector T cells in the spleen are activated. The spleen is a central lymphoid organ not associated with any body surface. As a result, splenic T cells have a “promiscuous” homing pattern and travel to many different sites including mucosal surfaces. Because most current vaccines are delivered parenterally, they rely on generating this strong systemic response. In such cases, protection of the mucosa is mediated by a migration of T cells into mucosal tissues or by antibodies entering damaged areas once the pathogen has breached the mucosal barrier. This indirect protection may work, but direct immunization of the mucosal lymphoid tissues is expected to be much more efficient. It is therefore logical to prevent such infections by administering vaccines in such a way that they either stimulate the intestinal or the nasopharyngeal lymphoid tissues.

Vaccination Through Oral Route

The immune system functions on the basis that microorganisms that invade the body must be eliminated before they cause damage. Organisms that penetrate the epithelial barriers are promptly detected, attacked, and destroyed by both innate and adaptive mechanisms. Immunoglobulin (Ig)A antibodies predominate in surface secretions. At least 80% of all plasma cells are found in the intestinal lamina propria, and together they produce more IgA than all other immunoglobulin isotypes combined. IgA is found in enormous amounts in saliva, intestinal fluid, nasal, and tracheal secretions, tears, milk, colostrum, urine, and the secretions of the urogenital tract. When animals are vaccinated against

organisms that invade the intestinal or respiratory tracts, it makes sense to stimulate a mucosal IgA response.

Once a protective IgA response has been generated, other difficulties may arise. For example, secondary immune responses are sometimes difficult to induce on surfaces, and multiple doses of vaccine may not increase the intensity or duration of the local immune response. This is not caused by any intrinsic defect but occurs because high levels of IgA can block antigen absorption and so prevent it from reaching antigen-presenting cells and memory cells. To trigger an IgA response, the vaccine antigen can simply be ingested or inhaled. Unfortunately, such vaccines are not always effective. Inactivated antigens administered orally fail to trigger an IgA response because they are immediately washed off or simply digested when applied to mucous membranes. The only way a significant IgA response can be triggered is to use live vaccines, in which the vaccine organism can invade mucous membranes. The vaccine must persist for a sufficient time to trigger an immune response yet not cause significant damage.

Intranasal Vaccination

The intranasal route of administration has advantages over oral administration in that the vaccine is not significantly diluted by nasal fluids, and not exposed to a low pH or to digestive enzymes. It is also more appropriate to administer a vaccine at the site of the organism's potential invasion route. Nasal associated lymphoid tissue is extensive. The collection of oronasal pharyngeal lymphoid tissue includes all the tonsillar tissue, cervical lymph nodes, in addition to M cells and intraepithelial dendritic cells capturing antigen in the nasal mucosa. Intranasal vaccines are available for infectious bovine rhinotracheitis, parainfluenza 3, and respiratory syncytial virus of cattle, *Streptococcus equi* infections in horses, feline herpesvirus, *Bordetella bronchiseptica*, calicivirus infections, canine parainfluenza and *Bordetella* infection.

